

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1835	Adolf Tobler	1857	1857	1910		Swiss-German linguist and philologist	1835-1910
1835	Walter William Skeat	1871		1897		British pre-eminent British philologist	1835-1912
1835	William Torrey Harris	1874		1906		American educator, philosopher, and lexicographer	1835-1909
1836	Lucian Müller	1869		1898		German classical scholar	1836-1898
1836	Signe Rink	1886	No	1909	w	Danish writer and ethnologist	1836-1909
1837	Carl Abel	1855		1906		German comparative philologist	1837-1906
1837	Vasily Radlov	1858	1858	1918		German-Russian founder of Turkology, a scientific study of Turkic peoples	1837-1918
1837	James Murray	1860	No	1915		British (Scottish) lexicographer and philologist, primary editor of the Oxford English Dictionary (OED)	1837-1915
1837	Alois Goldbacher	1867	1867	1909		Austrian classical philologist	1837-1924
1837	Alexandre Guilmant	1875		1911		French organist and composer	1837-1911
1838	Gustav Uhlig	1862	1862	1914		German educator and classical philologist	1838-1914
1838	Theodor Zahn	1867	1867	1913		German Protestant theologian, a biblical scholar	1838-1933
1838	Edwin Abbott Abbott	1869		1889		British English schoolmaster, theologian, and Anglican priest	1838-1926
1838	Ernst Johann Eitel	1870	1871	1908		German Protestant who became a notable missionary in China and civil servant in British Hong Kong, where he served as Inspector of Schools	1838-1908
1838	Vatroslav Jagić	1871	1871	1908		Croatian scholar of Slavic studies	1838-1923
1838	Jan Gebauer	1872	1872	1900		Czech significant expert on Czech studies and one of the most renowned Czech scientists of all times	1838-1907
1838	Robert Kennaway Douglas	1874		1913		British oriental scholar	1838-1913
1838	Marin Drinov	1875	1875	1906		Bulgarian historian and philologist	1838-1906
1838	Alice Cunningham Fletcher	1883		1916	w	American ethnologist, anthropologist, and social scientist who studied and documented American Indian culture	1838-1923
1839	Reinhard Kekulé von Stradonitz	1861	1861	1911		German archeologist, the founder of modern iconology (Langlotz)	1839-1911
1839	Johannes Schmeltz	1864	No	1909		German ethnographer and naturalist	1839-1909
1839	Frederic Ward Putnam	1865	1894	1909		American anthropologist, the " Father of American Archaeology "	1839-1915

1839 Edward William Brabrook	1869 No	1930	British English civil servant, author, and anthropologist with a special interest in folklore	1839-1930
1839 Isaac K. Funk	1878	1912	American Lutheran minister, editor, lexicographer, publisher, and spelling reformer	1839-1912